

Artificial intelligence and robotics in agriculture and allied areas - A study

P. K. Paul¹, A. Bhumali², R. R. Sinha³, P. S. Aithal⁴, R. Saavedra⁵, B. Aremu⁶

¹Department of CIS, Information Scientist (Offg.), Raiganj University, Raiganj, West Bengal, India,

²Vice Chancellor, Raiganj University, Raiganj, West Bengal, India,

³Pro Vice Chancellor (Asian Region), Commonwealth Vocational University, Makaunga, Tonga, Oceania,

⁴Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India,

⁵Director and Chair, International Inter-University Programs, Azteca University, México, North America,

⁶Vice Chancellor, Crown University Intl. Chartered Inc. Argentina Campus, South America

ABSTRACT

Technologies are changing radically; different organizations and institutions are using various core, allied technologies to make the things, systems, services, and product easier. The development of computing and information technology is changing massively; and as far as agriculture sector is concerned it is also increased in recent past. There are various technologies and systems in respect of agricultural promotion and development. Information technology is dedicated in information related activities in agriculture and allied activities. There are many reasons for the uses of IT and Computing in the Agriculture, namely, huge amount of crops, plants and agricultural product requirement, speed, disease detection, sustainable development promotion, and quality enhancement of agricultural products. Artificial intelligence (AI) powered solutions helps agricultural systems to do more in all sorts with less and further it helps in developing the quality of agro products and ensures faster go-to-market for crops. The complete agriculture landscape been changed by AI and there are many potentialities in regard to the applications of AI and allied technologies, namely, drone-based image processing and precision farming landscape. Different organizations, institutions associated with the agriculture are doing efforts on technological integration and especially AI due to its wider benefits. This paper is theoretical one and talks about the basics of AI and Robotics, Agricultural Informatics and specially applications of AI and Robotics in Agriculture and similar activities.

Keywords: Agricultural informatics, Artificial intelligence, ICT, Precision agriculture, Technological management

INTRODUCTION

Modern world is toward more smart, sophisticated and intelligent supported by various kinds of tools, technologies. Contemporary world becomes more scientific, modern, and technologically equipped with due to Information Technology and Computing in many contexts. Artificial intelligence (AI) is an important part of computing which is responsible for developing intelligent systems and also dedicated to developing intelligence powered by the machines and referred to as intelligent agents. Since AI is associated with the machines; therefore, it is also called machine intelligence; dedicated to learning and problem solving. Computational statistics is playing an important role in giving prediction by the use of computers. Mathematical optimization is here important with suitable methods, theory, and applications. Robotics is an interdisciplinary area and involves with intelligent systems and robots designing, construction, operation, etc. Among the components of IT few important are database technology, multimedia technology, network technology,

software technology, etc., and within these technologies, some sub, and emerging areas are booming, namely, AI, Big Data, Cloud Computing, Robotics, HCI, and so on. AI applications in other sectors and areas including agriculture developed the overall scenario (Aravind *et al.*, 2017; Paul *et al.*, 2013; Paul *et al.*, 2016). The need and huge amount of agricultural product requirements in coming age can only be solved by AI support. UN Food and Agriculture Organization has expressed that by 2050 the world population will reach to 2 billion and in this regard only 4% additional land can be cultivated then. The latest technological solutions promoting efficiency, greatest imperatives, etc., and it can be helpful in bringing a paradigm shift in how we see farming today.

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***Corresponding author:** P. K. Paul, Department of CIS, Information Scientist (Offg.), Raiganj University, Raiganj, West Bengal, India.
E-mail: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com